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The conceptualization groundwork for indicators of Interdisciplinarity – A closer look at section references

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Introduction & Background

Collaborations and interactions across boundaries has increasingly been recognized as important means to tackle the complexity of today’s societal challenges. Within the sciences, such boundary-crossing is manifested by different modes of interdisciplinary research (IDR), involving multi-, inter-, intra-, cross-, or transdisciplinary engagement of and with knowledge. Recognizing both the perceived scientific and societal promises of IDR (Huutoniemi & Rafols, 2017; Yegros-Yegros et al., 2015), as well as the systemic barriers against and individual and collaborative challenges with engaging in IDR (Davé et al., 2016), several scientific funding organizations have made IDR a key funding priority.

Much academic research has been devoted to better conceptualize, delineate and measure the phenomenon. In particular, bibliometric indicators have proliferated that define IDR in terms of knowledge integration at different levels of granularity. Usually, the focal dimension of knowledge integration is represented by diversity, which itself consists of three components: *variety* as the number of disciplinary categories, *balance* as the evenness of the distribution and *disparity* as the degree of difference between the categories (Rafols, 2014). Diversity measures either combine or separate those three components in capturing the degree of IDR as knowledge integration; following the cognitive approach, these are usually applied to the publication’s reference list, where the references are usually assigned to disciplinary categories via their journals.

Recently, systematic accounts have tackled methodological issues of consistency and made important contributions by comparing the influence of the “bibliometric groundwork” involved in identifying IDR (see Glänzel & Debackere, 2021 for an overview). Nonetheless, the basic premise of the cognitive approach, that knowledge integration as a manifestation of the interdisciplinary phenomenon can be measured and conceptualized by the diversity of the reference list has proven challenging.

On the one hand, there seems to be agreement that the phenomenon of IDR is multi-dimensional and multi-faceted in nature, where approaches and researcher decisions provide insights on one aspect at the expense of others. As such, fuzziness, ambiguity and contradictions can be viewed as reflective of this true nature of IDR (Glänzel & Debackere, 2021). On the other hand, the

proliferation of bibliometric approaches with a focus on methodological issues might have come at the expense of a comparative effort in the “conceptualization groundwork”, where the fuzziness and contradictions have not sufficiently been viewed as grounds to further reflect on the different types, degrees, epistemic values and definitions of IDR as previously advanced (Huutoniemi & Rafols, 2017; Marres & de Rijcke, 2020).

To contribute to these efforts, the idea is to discuss a bibliometric approach that might be better able to reflect differences in (inter-)disciplinary pathways and its manifestations. Instead of solely relying on the full reference list, the assumption advanced here and to be further developed and tested is that the sections of where those references occur and co-occur in a publication can be informative as to the type of knowledge integration reflected in the publication. Possible conceptual distinctions could be drawn between i.e. empirical, methodological and theoretical interdisciplinarity (Huutoniemi et al., 2010), depending on the distribution of the observed categories across those sections of the paper. We pose several questions at the intersection of the proposed approach, the conceptual challenge and existing indicators, that we aim to tackle during the research progress:

- Do we observe the different types of knowledge integration in interdisciplinary publications, i.e. ideas (concepts/ theories), methods (techniques, tools), data?
- Do we observe a co-occurrence of same or closely related subfields in a given section or are they distributed across sections?
- Do we observe the differential contribution of references to the type of knowledge integration, i.e. crucial, ancillary?

In the following, we describe the current stage of our data retrieval and data matching approach, as well as provide some preliminary, descriptive results.

Data & Methods

To operationalize our approach, we have used the ScienceDirect API to retrieve the full-text content from Elsevier publications, alongside the in-text references, the reference list and author-assigned section labels and headings. To conduct a first exploration of the approach, we have limited our data retrieval to five researchers, for which we have domain knowledge and therefore expected differences in the ways they engage in the integration of knowledge across domains. From the full publication history, we identify the subset of Elsevier publications for use in the API. Moreover, we match the retrieved reference lists with the publications that are indexed in the WoS.

For both the full set and the Elsevier subset of publications of the researchers, we calculate commonly used IDR indicators of variety/ balance and disparity. For this we rely on the journal classification at the level of granularity of 74 subfields according to the Leuven-Budapest subject classification scheme (Glänzel & Debackere, 2021) and the re-classification of publications in journals within multidisciplinary categories in up to three subfields using the multiple-generation reference model (Glänzel et al., 2021). For the calculation of disparity, we have relied on the cosine similarity between the 74 subfields in the period 2012-2017 based on Bibliographic Coupling.

Table 1 provides an overview of the publication profiles of those researchers, alongside the averages of IDR indicators over their individual publications, where publications by ALB draw on more different subfields more evenly, while publications by BVL combine on average more disparate subfields.

Table 1. Comparison of IDR indicators for five researchers

Researcher	WoS Publications	Avg. References	Primary Subfield	Variety/Balance (Hill)	Disparity (Leinster-Cobbold)
ALB	471	25.21	P6 - physics of solids, fluids and plasmas	4.10	19.17
DC	73	22.99	L1 - business, economics, planning	1.68	40.03
CH	57	14.28	L1 - business, economics, planning	3.75	25.85
BVL	69	43.35	L1 - business, economics, planning	2.34	49.51
BT	108	13.81	Y1 - education, media & information science	2.53	26.23

Results & Outlook

To explore the ‘interdisciplinary’ distribution of references across sections, Figure 1-3 show the references from Introduction to the Discussion/ Conclusion as they occur for an individual publication of the three researchers with primary disciplines in L1. Colours represent the high-level section, while the dot sizes are set according to the number of times a given reference is referenced. Table 2 supplements the visual information, where IDR indicators are shown for each of the high-level sections alongside the conventional IDR indicators using the full reference list.

While the DC publication (Fig.1) seems very much rooted in the core discipline of the researcher and the occurrence of other subfields are only resulting from references that belong to the primary subfield and another subfield (and do seem to be rather ancillary, judging by the rather small sizes), the BVL publication (Fig. 3) seems to engage more strongly with different subfields and also more directly, as not all multiple mentioned references are also tagged within L1; contrary to the Leinster-Cobbold disparity measure which varies much more strongly across sections for DC, for BVL it is more similar across sections. The CH publication (Fig.2), in addition to having its core in L1, seems to crucially rely on one publication that combines the very distinct subfields of L1, and Physics (P4/ P6) – the result of the individual article-level multiple-generation reference model by Glänzel et al., (2021) – which exerts a strong influence particularly on the section-dependent Leinster-Cobbold disparity measure.

Figure 1. Section distribution of references (DC)

Figure 2. Section distribution of references (CH)

Figure 3. Section distribution of references (BVL)

Together, this type of exploration seems to indeed be suggestive of different types of knowledge integration across subfields. While the DC publication shows little to none of this phenomenon, the BVL publication could suggest some limited theoretical and methodological integration, which is still very rooted in the dominant subfield. The CH publication would strongly suggest both theoretical and methodological integration, however the question indeed becomes, whether the knowledge integration is not rather rooted in the heavily cited source publication. We aim to address these questions more carefully and at a larger scale during our ongoing research.

Table 2. Comparison of IDR section indicators

Researcher	Publication Section				Full Publication		
	Heading	No. Ref	Hill	Leinster-Cobbold	No. Ref	Hill	Leinster-Cobbold
DC	1) Introduction	25	1.16	78.68	60	1.5	38.42
	2) Theoretical framework	5	1.28	41.64			
	3) Data and descriptive statistics	13	1.15	111.40			
	4) Empirical results	11	1.35	41.45			
	5) Discussion and conclusion	11	1.00	0.00			
CH	1) Introduction	11	3.68	75.81	22	2.6	80.23
	2) Connecting income inequality and economic development	9	2.32	82.97			
	3) Data and methods	1	2.00	21.97			
	4) The statistical connection between economic complexity and income inequality	6	2.50	127.02			
	5) The product space and income inequality	7	2.58	121.32			
	6) Discussion/concluding remarks	4	2.00	153.91			
	Appendix) Descriptive statistics	1	1.00	0.00			
BVL	1) Introduction	16	2.91	27.80	71	3.1	25.96
	2) Literature review	38	2.97	27.85			
	3) Data and methods	9	2.88	17.65			
	4) Control variables	3	3.00	22.65			
	6) Conclusions and discussion	12	2.33	20.17			

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